

Supplementary material 7 Analyses

Summary of findings important outcomes

Studies: RCTs								
Patient or population: adult women undergoing single or bilateral breast surgery for malignant diseases in a hospital or in the outpatient setting								
Interventions: erector spinae plane block, pectoral nerve block (I or II), or serratus anterior plane block								
Comparison: paravertebral block								
Outcomes: quality of recovery (at day one), time to first analgesic request, postoperative opioid use (at 24 and 48 hours and total), postoperative NSAID use (at 24 hours and total), and postoperative nausea and vomiting (at 24 and 48 hours and total)								
Outcomes	Number of RCTs (number of patients)	Regional analgesia technique	NMA effect estimate (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effect (95% CI)		SUCRA ranking	Certainty of evidence ^c	Reasons for downgrading
				Paravertebral block	Other block type			
				Assumed risk ^a	Corresponding risk ^b			
Quality of recovery on day one (patient satisfaction score)	3 (206)	ESPB	SMD 0 (-1.41 to 1.41)		Mean patient satisfaction score at day 1 with ESPB was equal to with PVB (1.41 standard deviations lower to 1.41 higher)	1	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		SAPB	SMD -0.01 (-1.74 to 1.72)		Mean patient satisfaction score at day 1 with ESPB was 0.01 standard deviations lower than with PVB (1.74 lower to 1.72 higher)	3	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator				2	

Quality of recovery on day two	Not reported by any study.							
Quality of recovery on day three	Not reported by any study.							
Time to first analgesic request (in minutes)	11 (713)	ESP	MD 6.47 (-74.44 to 87.39)	Mean time to first analgesic request was 451.32 minutes	Mean time to first analgesic request with ESPB was 6.47 minutes longer than with PVB (74.44 shorter to 87.39 longer)	3	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		PEC	MD 122.72 (36.91 to 208.52)		Mean time to first analgesic request with PEC was 122.72 minutes longer than with PVB (36.91 longer to 208.52 longer)	1	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Heterogeneity (-2 levels)
		SAPB	MD 61.35 (-33.56 to 156.27)		Mean time to first analgesic request with SAPB was 61.35 minutes longer than with PVB (33.56 shorter to 156.27 longer)	2	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Imprecision (-2 levels); indirect evidence only (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator				4	
Postoperative opioid use at two hours	Not reported by any study.							
Postoperative opioid use at 24 hours	11 (622)	ESP	SMD 0.23 (-1.06 to 1.52)		Mean postoperative opioid use at 24 hours with ESPB was 0.23 standard deviations higher than with PVB	4	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)

					(1.06 lower to 1.52 higher)			
		PEC	SMD -0.86 (-2.34 to 0.62)		Mean postoperative opioid use at 24 hours with PEC was 0.86 standard deviations lower than with PVB (2.34 lower to 0.62 higher)	1	⊕⊕⊕⊖ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		SAPB	SMD 0.41 (-1.97 to 2.80)		Mean postoperative opioid use at 24 hours with ESPB was 0.41 standard deviations higher than with PVB (1.97 lower to 2.80 higher)	3	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Imprecision (-2 levels); indirect evidence only (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator			2		
Postoperative opioid use at 48 hours	1 (60)	ESPB	SMD 0.20 (-0.42 to 0.82)		Mean postoperative opioid use at 48 hours with ESPB was 0.20 standard deviations higher than with PVB (0.42 lower to 0.82 higher)		⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	No NMA performed (very low certainty of evidence)
		PEC	SMD -0.19 (-0.81 to 0.43)		Mean postoperative opioid use at 48 hours with PEC was 0.19 standard deviations lower than with PVB (0.81 lower to 0.43 higher)		⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	No NMA performed (very low certainty of evidence)

		PVB	Comparator					
Postoperative opioid use total	9 (478)	ESP	SMD -0.19 (-1.38 to 1.00)		Mean total postoperative opioid use with ESPB was 0.19 standard deviations lower than with PVB (1.38 lower to 1.00 higher)	2	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		PEC	SMD -0.93 (-2.28 to 0.42)		Mean total postoperative opioid use with PEC was 0.93 standard deviations lower than with PVB (2.28 lower to 0.42 higher)	1	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		SAPB	SMD 0.87 (-0.97 to 2.72)		Mean total postoperative opioid use with SAPB was 0.87 standard deviations higher than with PVB (0.97 lower to 2.72 higher)	4	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		PVB	Comparator			3		
Postoperative NSAID use at two hours	Not reported by any study.							
Postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours	2 (160)	ESP	SMD -0.14 (-0.58 to 0.30)		Mean postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours with ESPB was 0.14 standard deviations lower than with PVB (0.58 lower to 0.30 higher)	2	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)

		SAPB	SMD -0.53 (-1.15 to 0.09)		Mean postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours with SAPB was 0.53 standard deviations lower than with PVB (1.15 lower to 0.09 higher)	1	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator			3		
Postoperative NSAID use at 48 hours	Not reported by any study.							
Postoperative NSAID use total	2 (120)	ESPB	SMD -0.14 (-0.58 to 0.30)		Mean total postoperative NSAID use with ESPB was 0.14 standard deviations lower than with PVB (0.58 lower to 0.30 higher)	2	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		SAPB	SMD -1.71 (-2.43 to -0.98)		Mean total postoperative NSAID use with SAPB was 1.71 standard deviations lower than with PVB (2.43 lower to 0.98 lower)	1	⊕⊖⊖⊖ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator			3		
Postoperative nausea and vomiting at two hours	Not reported by any study.							
Postoperative nausea and	5 (385)	ESPB	RR 1.74 (0.56-5.43)	77 per 1000	134 per 1000 (43 to 418)	4	⊕⊕⊖⊖ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)

vomiting at 24 hours		PEC	RR 0.83 (0.13-5.26)	77 per 1000	64 per 1000 (10 to 405)	1	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Imprecision (-2 levels); indirect evidence only (very low certainty of evidence)
		SAPB	RR 1.59 (0.41-6.22)	77 per 1000	122 per 1000 (32 to 479)	3	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Imprecision (-2 levels); indirect evidence only (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator			2		
Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 48 hours	2 (104)	ESPB	RR 1.67 (0.31-8.93)	95 per 1000	159 per 1000 (29 to 848)	3	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		PEC	RR 1.61 (0.26-10.14)	95 per 1000	153 per 1000 (25 to 963)	2	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Very low)	Heterogeneity and incoherence not estimated due to low number of studies (very low certainty of evidence)
		PVB	Comparator			1		
Postoperative nausea and vomiting total	7 (449)	ESPB	RR 1.44 (0.53-3.94)	134 per 1000	193 (71 to 528)	4	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		PEC	RR 0.85 (0.24-3.03)	134 per 1000	114 (32 to 406)	2	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		SAPB	RR 0.59 (0.13-2.67)	134 per 1000	79 (17 to 358)	1	⊕⊕⊕⊕ (Low)	Imprecision (-2 levels)
		PVB	Comparator			3		

RCT: randomised controlled trial; NMA: network meta-analysis; SUCRA: surface under the cumulative ranking; ESPB: erector spinae plane block; PEC: pectoral nerve block; SAPB: serratus anterior plane block; PVB: paravertebral block; MD: mean difference; SMD: standardised mean difference; RR: risk ratio; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

^aCalculated based of total number of events in the paravertebral block groups in the studies included in NMA.

^bCalculated based on NMA estimate and 95% CI and assumed risk in comparator group.

^cCertainty of evidence was assessed with CINeMA, the online tool - Confidence in Network Meta-analysis. Certainty of evidence was downgraded by one level for domains with some concerns and two levels for domains with major concerns. Outcomes relying solely on indirect evidence, reported by a single study, or with heterogeneity and incoherence that could not be estimated due to a low number of studies in NMA were rated as very low certainty. The domains within-study bias, reporting bias, and indirectness were scored as no concerns for each outcome. A detailed explanation of the methodology for the rating of each domain can be found in the methods section, and the CINeMa ratings for each outcome can be found in Table 2.

Imprecision (one side of the 95% CI extended into or beyond the area of equivalence (based on the MCID) on the opposite side of the no-effect line) was the reason for downgrading the certainty of evidence for time to first analgesic request (ESPB and SAPB versus PVB), postoperative opioid use at 24 hours (ESPB, PEC, and SAPB versus PVB), total postoperative opioid use (ESPB, PEC, and SAPB versus PVB), PONV at 24 hours (ESPB, PEC, and SAPB versus PVB), and total PONV (ESPB, PEC, and SAPB versus PVB). Heterogeneity (the 95% PI suggested a different conclusion than the 95% CI) was the reason for downgrading the certainty of evidence for time to first analgesic request (PEC versus PVB). The availability of indirect evidence only was the reason for downgrading the certainty of evidence for time to first analgesic request (SAPB versus PVB), postoperative opioid use at 24 hours (SAPB versus PVB), and PONV at 24 hours (PEC and SAPB versus PVB). A low number of studies and consequently the inability to estimate heterogeneity and incoherence was the reason for downgrading the evidence for quality of recovery at day 1 (ESPB and SAPB versus PVB), postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours (ESPB and SAPB versus PVB), total postoperative NSAID use (ESPB and SAPB versus PVB), and PONV at 48 hours (ESPB and PEC versus PVB). Finally, for postoperative opioid use at 48 hours (ESPB and PEC versus PVB), the certainty of evidence was downgraded because no NMA was performed due to only one available study.

Interpretation of league tables

League tables in network meta-analysis (NMA) summarise pairwise comparisons between treatments, presenting effect sizes such as risk ratios (RR), mean differences (MD), or standardized mean differences (SMD), along with 95% confidence intervals. Each column and row represent a treatment, with the intersecting cell displaying the effect of the column treatment relative to the row treatment. For RRs, values less than 1 indicate that the column treatment is associated with a lower risk than the row treatment. For MDs and SMDs, a positive or negative value indicates the magnitude of difference calculated as column value minus row value. Confidence intervals reflect the uncertainty of these estimates, and results are statistically significant if the interval does not cross the null value (e.g., 1 for RRs or 0 for MDs and SMDs).

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DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Primary analysis

Postoperative pain at 2 hours at rest

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.12 (-0.31; 0.07)	Paravertebral block		
0.36 (0.15; 0.56)	0.47 (0.22; 0.73)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.38 (-0.23; 1.00)	0.50 (-0.09; 1.09)	0.03 (-0.61; 0.66)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative pain at 2 hours with movement

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.46 (-1.24; 0.33)	Paravertebral block	
0.60 (-0.52; 1.72)	1.06 (0.14; 1.98)	Pectoral nerve block

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Postoperative pain at 24 hours at rest

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.15 (-0.35; 0.05)	Paravertebral block		
0.17 (-0.07; 0.41)	0.32 (0.03; 0.61)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.01 (-0.20; 0.22)	0.16 (-0.10; 0.42)	-0.16 (-0.41; 0.09)	Serratus anterior plane block

Funnel plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818. DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

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Postoperative pain at 24 hours with movement

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.09 (-0.48; 0.31)	Paravertebral block		
-0.17 (-0.75; 0.42)	-0.08 (-0.64; 0.48)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.24 (-0.68; 0.19)	-0.16 (-0.69; 0.38)	-0.07 (-0.63; 0.48)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative pain at 48 hours at rest

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block	
0.18 (-0.31; 0.67)	Paravertebral block

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Postoperative pain at 48 hours with movement

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
0.13 (-0.55; 0.81)	Paravertebral block	
0.20 (-0.55; 0.95)	0.07 (-0.29; 0.43)	Pectoral nerve block

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

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Quality of recovery (day one)

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.00 (-1.41; 1.41)	Paravertebral block	
0.01 (-0.99; 1.01)	0.01 (-1.72; 1.74)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Time to first analgesic request

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
6.47 (-74.44; 87.39)	Paravertebral block		
-116.24 (-195.24; -37.24)	-122.72 (-208.52; -36.91)	Pectoral nerve block	
-54.88 (-139.07; 29.32)	-61.35 (-156.27; 33.56)	61.36 (-32.55; 155.28)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Funnel plot

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Postoperative opioid use at 24 hours

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.23 (-1.06; 1.52)	Paravertebral block		
1.09 (-0.10; 2.28)	0.86 (-0.62; 2.34)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.18 (-2.19; 1.83)	-0.41 (-2.80; 1.97)	-1.27 (-3.61; 1.06)	Serratus anterior plane block

Funnel plot

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Postoperative opioid use at 48 hours

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
0.20 (-0.42; 0.82)	Paravertebral block	
0.39 (-0.24; 1.01)	0.19 (-0.43; 0.81)	Pectoral nerve block

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Postoperative opioid use total

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.19 (-1.38; 1.00)	Paravertebral block		
0.74 (-0.40; 1.88)	0.93 (-0.42; 2.28)	Pectoral nerve block	
-1.07 (-2.91; 0.78)	-0.87 (-2.72; 0.97)	-1.80 (-3.87; 0.26)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.14 (-0.58; 0.30)	Paravertebral block	
0.39 (-0.05; 0.84)	0.53 (-0.09; 1.15)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative NSAID use total

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.14 (-0.58; 0.30)	Paravertebral block	
1.57 (0.72; 2.42)	1.71 (0.98; 2.43)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 24 hours

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
1.74 (0.56; 5.43)	Paravertebral block		
2.10 (0.49; 8.99)	1.20 (0.19; 7.62)	Pectoral nerve block	
1.09 (0.52; 2.32)	0.63 (0.16; 2.45)	0.52 (0.13; 2.09)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 48 hours

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
1.67 (0.31; 8.93)	Paravertebral block	
1.03 (0.16; 6.49)	0.62 (0.10; 3.89)	Pectoral nerve block

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Postoperative nausea and vomiting total

Network plot

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
1.44 (0.53; 3.94)	Paravertebral block		
1.69 (0.48; 5.94)	1.17 (0.33; 4.15)	Pectoral nerve block	
2.43 (0.46; 12.99)	1.69 (0.37; 7.59)	1.44 (0.30; 6.81)	Serratus anterior plane block

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Sensitivity analysis

NRS/VAS at 2 hours at rest

Network plot

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Forest plot

NRS/VAS at 2 hours at rest versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 23; number of patients: 1303; I^2 : 79.3%. Two studies were not included in the network meta-analysis. One study reported no significant difference between serratus anterior plane block and erector spinae plane block (1), and the other study reported no significant difference between paravertebral block and serratus anterior plane block (2).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.16 (-0.49; 0.17)	Paravertebral block		
0.06 (-0.27; 0.39)	0.22 (-0.09; 0.53)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.08 (-0.47; 0.31)	0.07 (-0.36; 0.51)	-0.14 (-0.59; 0.30)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.7870), erector spinae plane block (0.6013), serratus anterior plane block (0.3940), and paravertebral block (0.2177).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 2 hours with movement

Network plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Forest plot

NRS/VAS at 2 hours with movement versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 6; number of patients: 406; I^2 : 80.3%. One study was not included in the network meta-analysis, but reported no significant difference between serratus anterior plane block and erector spinae plane block (1).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.34 (-1.11; 0.43)	Paravertebral block		
0.88 (-0.04; 1.81)	1.22 (0.36; 2.09)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.10 (-1.19; 1.39)	0.44 (-1.06; 1.94)	-0.78 (-2.37; 0.80)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.9373), serratus anterior plane block (0.4873), erector spinae plane block (0.4317), and paravertebral block (0.1437).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 24 hours at rest

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 24 hours at rest versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 27; number of patients: 1579; I^2 : 77.9%. Five studies were not included in the network meta-analysis. One study reported a significantly lower NRS score in the pectoral nerve block group compared to the erector spinae plane block group (3). One study reported a significantly lower VAS score in the serratus anterior plane block group compared to the pectoral nerve block group (4). One study reported a significantly lower NRS score in the erector spinae plane block group compared to the pectoral nerve block group (5). One study reported no significant difference in VAS score between the paravertebral block and serratus anterior plane block groups (2). Finally, one study reported no significant difference in VAS score between the pectoral nerve block and paravertebral block groups (6).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.04 (-0.25; 0.32)	Paravertebral block		
-0.01 (-0.33; 0.31)	-0.05 (-0.33; 0.24)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.06 (-0.39; 0.27)	-0.09 (-0.47; 0.28)	-0.05 (-0.43; 0.34)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.6407), erector spinae plane block (0.5373), pectoral nerve block (0.4770), and serratus anterior plane block (0.3450).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 24 hours with movement

Network plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Forest plot

NRS/VAS at 24 hours with movement versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 11; number of patients: 765; I^2 : 89.3%. Two studies were not included in the network-meta-analysis. One study reported that the NRS score was significantly lower in the erector spinae plane block group compared to the pectoral nerve block group (5), the other study reported no significant difference between pectoral nerve block and paravertebral block (7).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.23 (-0.35; 0.81)	Paravertebral block		
-0.28 (-0.93; 0.38)	-0.51 (-1.14; 0.13)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.22 (-0.82; 0.39)	-0.44 (-1.23; 0.34)	0.06 (-0.70; 0.82)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.8697), erector spinae plane block (0.5820), serratus anterior plane block (0.3293), and pectoral nerve block (0.2190).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 48 hours at rest

Network plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Forest plot

NRS/VAS at 48 hours at rest versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 4; number of patients: 245; I^2 : 68.4%. One study was not included in the network meta-analysis, but reported no significant difference in VAS score between the paravertebral block and serratus anterior plane block groups (2).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.18 (-0.93; 1.29)	Paravertebral block		
0.11 (-1.29; 1.50)	-0.07 (-0.92; 0.77)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.10 (-1.16; 0.96)	-0.28 (-1.81; 1.25)	-0.21 (-1.96; 1.54)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.6407), erector spinae plane block (0.5373), pectoral nerve block (0.4770), and serratus anterior plane block (0.3450).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

NRS/VAS at 48 hours with movement

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Paravertebral block versus other block type regarding NRS/VAS at 48 hours with movement. Number of studies: 3; number of patients: 204; I²: 0%.

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.13 (-0.55; 0.81)	Paravertebral block		
0.20 (-0.55; 0.95)	0.07 (-0.29; 0.43)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.00 (-0.47; 0.47)	-0.13 (-0.96; 0.70)	-0.20 (-1.08; 0.68)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.6597), paravertebral block (0.5870), serratus anterior plane block (0.3930), and erector spinae plane block (0.3603).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Block failure

Network plot

Forest plot

Block failure versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 15; number of patients: 918; I^2 : 0%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
1.00 (0.29-3.50)	Paravertebral block		
1.16 (0.28-4.79)	1.15 (0.34-3.86)	Pectoral nerve block	
1.51 (0.33-6.83)	1.50 (0.43-5.27)	1.30 (0.37-4.63)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: serratus anterior plane block (0.7087), pectoral nerve block (0.4790), erector spinae plane block (0.4213), and paravertebral block (0.3910).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Hypotension

Network plot

Forest plot

Hypotension versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 20; number of patients: 1154; I^2 : 0%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.51 (0.18; 1.49)	Paravertebral block		
1.21 (0.33; 4.45)	2.35 (0.80; 6.92)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.66 (0.12; 3.57)	1.28 (0.28; 5.93)	0.54 (0.09; 3.20)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.7740), erector spinae plane block (0.6497), serratus anterior plane block (0.3887), and paravertebral block (0.1877).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Pneumothorax

Network plot

Forest plot

Pneumothorax versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 21; number of patients: 1289; I^2 : 0%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.58 (0.18; 1.90)	Paravertebral block		
0.79 (0.20; 3.16)	1.37 (0.41; 4.57)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.72 (0.16; 3.35)	1.25 (0.31; 5.13)	0.92 (0.18; 4.57)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: erector spinae plane block (0.7083), pectoral nerve block (0.5310), serratus anterior plane block (0.4640), and paravertebral block (0.2967).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Quality of recovery day 1

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Quality of recovery (patient satisfaction score) on day one versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 7; number of patients: 464; I^2 : 58.9%. One study was not included in the network meta-analysis, but reported no significant difference in quality of recovery at day 1(8).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.11 (-0.64; 0.42)	Paravertebral block		
-0.08 (-0.77; 0.61)	0.03 (-0.42; 0.48)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.01 (-0.55; 0.52)	0.10 (-0.65; 0.85)	0.07 (-0.80; 0.95)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.6143), pectoral nerve block (0.5310), serratus anterior plane block (0.4550), and erector spinae plane block (0.3997).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Time to first analgesic request

Network plot

Forest plot

Time to first analgesic request versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 23; number of patients: 1335; I^2 : 95.5%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
9.45 (-44.38; 63.28)	Paravertebral block		
-67.04 (-130.75; -3.34)	-76.49 (-132.55; -20.43)	Pectoral nerve block	
-17.00 (-82.11; 48.10)	-26.45 (-98.39; 45.48)	50.04 (-26.54; 126.62)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.9620), serratus anterior plane block (0.5127), erector spinae plane block (0.3233), and paravertebral block (0.2020).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative opioid use at 24 hours

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative opioid use at 24 hours versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 28; number of patients: 1684; I²: 93.2%. One study was not included in the network-meta-analysis, but reported no significant difference in postoperative opioid use at 24 hours between the paravertebral block and erector spinae plane block groups (9).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
0.31 (-0.30; 0.92)	Paravertebral block		
0.74 (0.13; 1.35)	0.43 (-0.19; 1.05)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.14 (-0.54; 0.82)	-0.17 (-0.93; 0.59)	-0.60 (-1.38; 0.18)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.942), paravertebral block (0.542), serratus anterior planer block (0.338), and erector spinae plane block (0.178).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative opioid use at 48 hours

Network plot

Forest plot

Postoperative opioid use at 48 hours versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 5; number of patients: 311; I²: 97.9%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
2.46 (-0.93; 5.85)	Paravertebral block		
1.83 (-1.80; 5.47)	-0.63 (-3.14; 1.88)	Pectoral nerve block	
3.57 (-0.01; 7.15)	1.11 (-2.45; 4.67)	1.74 (-2.35; 5.82)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: serratus anterior plane block (0.8380), paravertebral block (0.6227), pectoral nerve block (0.4537), and erector spinae plane block (0.0857).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative opioid use total

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Total postoperative opioid use versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 26; number of patients: 1416; I^2 : 90.9%.

Two studies were not included in the network meta-analysis. Both studies reported no significant difference in postoperative total opioid use between the paravertebral block and erector spinae plane block groups (9, 10).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
-0.04 (-0.68; 0.60)	Paravertebral block		
0.57 (-0.09; 1.22)	0.60 (0.00; 1.21)	Pectoral nerve block	
-0.28 (-1.02; 0.46)	-0.24 (-1.02; 0.53)	-0.85 (-1.67; -0.03)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.9723), erector spinae plane block (0.4477), paravertebral block (0.4000), and serratus anterior plane block (0.1800).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours

Network plot

Forest plot

Postoperative NSAID use at 24 hours versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 2; number of patients: 160; I^2 : NA.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.14 (-0.58; 0.30)	Paravertebral block	
0.39 (-0.05; 0.84)	0.53 (-0.09; 1.15)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: serratus anterior plane block (0.9505), erector spinae plane block (0.3920), and paravertebral block (0.1575).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative NSAID use total

Network plot

Forest plot

Total postoperative opioid use versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 2; number of patients: 120; I²: NA.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
-0.14 (-0.58; 0.30)	Paravertebral block	
1.57 (0.72; 2.42)	1.71 (0.98; 2.43)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: serratus anterior plane block (1.000), erector spinae plane block (0.359), and paravertebral block (0.141).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 24 hours

Network plot

Forest plot

Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 24 hours versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 12; number of patients: 785; I^2 : 0%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
1.07 (0.63; 1.83)	Paravertebral block		
1.36 (0.75; 2.48)	1.27 (0.59; 2.74)	Pectoral nerve block	
0.92 (0.51; 1.65)	0.85 (0.39; 1.88)	0.67 (0.31; 1.47)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: pectoral nerve block (0.8160), paravertebral block (0.5067), erector spinae plane block (0.3900), and serratus anterior plane block (0.2873).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 48 hours

Network plot

Forest plot

Postoperative nausea and vomiting at 48 hours versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 3; number of patients: 164; I²: 0%.

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

League table

Erector spinae plane block		
1.27 (0.44; 3.63)	Paravertebral block	
0.99 (0.35; 2.83)	0.78 (0.37; 1.63)	Pectoral nerve block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.7140), erector spinae plane block (0.4225), and pectoral nerve block (0.3635).

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Postoperative nausea and vomiting total

Network plot

Forest plot

Clephas PRD, Orbach-Zinger S, Gosteli-Peter MA, Hoshen M, Halpern S, Hilber ND., Leo C, Heesen M. Regional analgesia with or without general anaesthesia for postoperative pain after breast cancer surgery: a network meta-analysis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* TBD, Issue TBD. Art. No.CD014818.

DOI: [10.1002/14651858.CD014818](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD014818).

Total postoperative nausea and vomiting versus paravertebral block. Number of studies: 23; number of patients: 1456; I²: 31%.

League table

Erector spinae plane block			
1.23 (0.76; 2.00)	Paravertebral block		
1.06 (0.64; 1.75)	0.86 (0.55; 1.35)	Pectoral nerve block	
1.22 (0.69; 2.15)	0.99 (0.57; 1.72)	1.15 (0.65; 2.04)	Serratus anterior plane block

The SUCRA ranking from best to worst was: paravertebral block (0.6893), serratus anterior plane block (0.6293), pectoral nerve block (0.4070), and erector spinae plane block (0.2743).

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